

20-cm spacing. Low temperature tolerance was measured in terms of spikelet sterility and yield. No serious stress was observed before the preanthesis period.

The 1987 yields showed strong varietal differences with altitude. Eleven genotypes produced grain at 2,000 m (Table 1). At 1,400 m, 17 genotypes produced grain. Minimum (night) temperatures ranged from 12.9 to 16.9 °C and maximum (day) temperatures from 23.5 to 23.9 °C. Water temperatures of the higher altitude sites were cooler (18.5-22.1 °C) than water temperatures at 1,000 m (23.9-25.3 °C) at anthesis. Water tem-

perature at anthesis at the 1,000-m site appears to be warmer than the critical limit for low temperature stress-induced sterility. We believe sterility and poor yield performance were associated with low temperature stress.

Yields in 1988 were higher than in 1987 (Table 2). Fifteen varieties produced some yield at 1,400 m. Spikelet sterility in these cultivars was low. Six exotic lines also showed some low temperature tolerance. But at 1,400 m, more than half the varieties evaluated failed to set grain.

We think the better performance of most of the low temperature-tolerant

varieties at 1,400 m can be associated with the relatively warmer water temperatures at anthesis in 1988 (22.1-21.2 °C) than in 1987 (19.0-18.5 °C).

At 1,250 m, 23 genotypes produced some yield. At 1,000 m, almost all varieties showed no symptoms of low temperature stress. Yields of IR7167-33-2-3-3 and NR15579-24-2 were best at lower altitudes. Varieties that perform better in the high hills (Chhomro, Ghara, Himali, Banahun, Raksali, and Seto Bhakunde) had comparatively poor yields in the lower elevations.

Local varieties Chhomro, Ghandruk, Himali Marshi, Ghara, Banahun, and Seto Bhakunde were identified as having low temperature tolerance. They could be used in breeding programs or extended into areas lacking adapted cultivars. ■

Table 1. Performance of low temperature-tolerant rice cultivars at 3 altitudes (1000-2000 m).^a Nepal, 1987.

Cultivar	2000 m		1400 m		1000 m	
	Grain yield (t/ha)	Spikelet sterility (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Spikelet sterility (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Spikelet sterility (%)
Ghandruk local	6.0	1	2.4	1	3.2	1
Himali Marshi	4.8	1	2.5	1	1.3	1
Ghara Local	4.0	1	3.7	1	2.9	1
Chhomro local (check)	3.7	1	3.2	3	0.5	1
Kalo Dhan	2.7	5	-	-	6.8	1
Banahun local	1.8	3	2.4	1	3.2	1
Seto Bhakunde	1.6	5	2.3	5	2.9	1
RP1442-8-2-1-2	1.2	7	-	-	3.2	1
Jumli Marshi	1.2	7	-	9	0.5	1
NR1066-1	0.8	7	-	-	0.5	1
(NRCTN, 1987 ^b) (n = 110)	(0-6)	(1-9)	(0-3.7)	(1-9)	(0.5-8.3)	(1-5)

^a Gram yield adjusted to 12% moisture. ^b Spikelet sterility at growth stage 8-9 rated by this scale: 1 = <1%, 3 = 1-5%, 5 = 5-25%, 7 = 25-50%. 9 = 50-100% spikelet sterility. ^c National Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery.

Table 2. Performance of low temperature-tolerant rice varieties at 3 altitudes.^a Nepal, 1988.

Genotype	1400 m		1250 m		1000 m	
	Grain yield (t/ha)	Spikelet sterility (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Spikelet sterility (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Spikelet sterility (%)
Chhomro local (check)	7.6	1	3.7	1	2.5	1
Ghara	6.1	3	2.6	1	2.0	1
Himali Marshi	6.0	1	5.0	1	1.7	1
Banahun local	5.4	1	2.5	1	1.8	1
NR10073-167-3-1	4.7	3	3.6	1	3.1	1
IR8866-393-14-2	4.3	3	5.1	1	4.4	1
IR7167-33-2-3-3	4.0	3	5.1	1	5.5	1
NR15579-24-2	3.3	3	2.2	3	5.2	3
RP1442-8-2-1-2	2.9	3	4.1	1	2.1	1
Raksali (check)	2.9	3	4.6	1	1.7	1
Seto Bhakunde	1.9	7	1.7	1	4.4	1
IR9202-6-1-1	1.9	3	3.5	1	2.0	1
Barkhe-2	1.5	5	1.8	1	3.2	1
Pokhareli Masino	1.4	7	3.4	1	4.2	1
BG400-1	1.0	7	3.1	1	2.5	1
NRCTN, 1988 (n = 33)	(0-7.6)	(1-9)	(1.6-5.5)	(1-5)	(1.2-5.6)	(1-3)

^a Grain yield adjusted to 12% moisture. Spikelet sterility (at growth stage 8-9) rated by the scale in Table 1.

Integrated germplasm improvement — irrigated

CICA8 and ITA222, new rice varieties for irrigated areas of Mbo Plain in West Cameroon

M. P. Jones and D. Janakiram, National Cereals Research and Extension Project, Dschang; and F. Jeutong and J. A. Ayuk Takem, Institut de la Recherche Agronomique (IRA), B.P. 44, Dschang, Cameroon

Mbo Plain, an area of about 30,000 ha, is in the West Province of Cameroon at 700 m altitude. About 10,000 ha are potentially suitable for rice cultivation, but only 210 ha are currently under irrigated production.

Major constraints are the disease susceptibility and grain characteristics of the currently grown variety Tainan V.

Although it is susceptible to leaf blast (BI) at early vegetative stages, Tainan V has the ability to recover and yields close to 4 t/ha in farmers' fields (Table 1). However, its short and bold grain, chalkiness, and cooking quality are not favored by urban consumers, causing difficulty in marketing.

To find varieties with higher yielding ability, B1 resistance, and acceptable grain quality, we have screened more than 6,000 varieties or lines since 1982. Most of the lines rated as resistant or moderately resistant to B1 in other parts of the world were found to be susceptible at Mbo Plain. (Climatic conditions there are highly conducive to B1.) A few entries, including ITA222 and CICA8, were found to be moderately resistant to both leaf and neck B1, with consistently higher yields than Tainan V, and superior grain quality (Table 1).

ITA222, a derivative of Mashir/IET1444 from the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture, has medium duration, medium height, good tillering ability, and an upright flag leaf. Its grains are long, with translucent kernels and flaky cooked texture (Table 2).

CICA8, a derivative of CICA4//IR665/Tetep from Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical, is shorter and has a longer growth duration than ITA222 and Tainan V. It has long, slender, translucent grains, which makes it competitive with imported rice in the ur-

Table 1. Yields of ITA222, CICA8, and Tainan V on-station and in farmers' fields at Mbo Plain, West Cameroon, 1985-88.

Variety	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)									
	On-station					On farm				
	1985	1986	1987	1988	Mean	1985	1986	1987	1988	Mean
ITA222	5.8	7.5	5.8	4.8	5.9	5.8	6.1	5.1	4.4	5.4
CICA 8	5.8	5.4	5.8	4.8	5.8	4.8	4.8	4.7	4.4	4.7
Tainan V (check)	8.4	4.1	8.9	4.2	5.6	8.7	8.5	8.8	8.0	8.4

^a Mean of 5 on-station and 5 on-farm trials each year.

Table 2. Characteristics of ITA222, CICA8, and Tainan V at Mbo Plain, Cameroon, 1985-88.

Variety	Plant height (cm)	Growth duration (d)	Reaction ^a to		
			Leaf blast	Neck blast	Grain type ^b
ITA222	95	104	MR	MS	L/S
CICA8	90	111	MR	MS	L/S
Tainan V (check)	108	95	S	MR	S/B

^a By the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. MR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible. ^b L/S = long and slender, S/B = short and bold.

ban market. CICA8 was released in 1985 to replace Tainan V and is now widely grown at Mbo Plain.

ITA222 is in the pipeline for release, but like CICA8 and other promising va-

rieties, it shows increasing susceptibility to leaf and neck B1. Average B1 scores for CICA8 and ITA222 were 5.5 and 4.5, respectively, in 1988 compared with 3.0 in 1986. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement – rainfed

IET8717, a physiologically efficient rice variety for waterlogged areas of Assam

K. Chandra, *Regional Agricultural Research Station, Titabar 30*; and S. C. Dey and Pradip ch. Dey, *Crop Physiology and Agricultural Botany Department, Assam Agricultural University, Jorhat 785013, India*

IET8717 is a long-duration, high-yielding rice variety developed from TN1/Lua Ngu by the Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad, India. It is suitable for waterlogged conditions.

We tested IET8717 and other promising long-duration cultivars, and Manoharsali as check, under continuous waterlogged conditions (30-50 cm water depth) in the 1988 wet season (Jul-Nov). Entries were transplanted at 20- × 20-cm spacing. Forty kg N as urea was applied in three equal splits: 1 d before transplanting, 20 d after transplanting, and at panicle

initiation. The plants received a basal application of 8.8 kg P as single super-phosphate and 16.6 kg K as muriate of potash.

Table 1. Physical and physiological characteristics of IET8717 and Manoharsali. Titabar, Assam, India, 1988.

Character	IET8717	Manoharsali
Duration (d)	144	157
Height (cm)	116	133
Panicles/m ²	271	264
Grains/panicle	205	132
1000-grain wt (g)	19.05	19.08
Total dry matter at maturity (g/hill)	39.0	45.0
Grain yield (t/ha)	5.3	2.7
Harvest index	0.55	0.40
Postflowering photosynthetic contribution (%)	70.0	48.0
N content of leaves at flowering (%)	1.96	1.72
Total chlorophyll content at flowering (mg/g FW)	4.18	3.58
Proportion of high-density grain (%)	63.66	50.60

Duration of IET8717 was 144 d. It had 271 productive panicles/m², with 6.8% tiller mortality. Its grains were medium slender, with white kernels, and 1,000-grain weight of 19 g. Plant height was 115 cm with leaf area index of 6.6 at flowering, and harvest index of 0.55. High postflowering photosynthetic contribution (70%) results in higher panicle and grain numbers/m². Yield was 5.3 t/ha (Table 1).

IET8717 has shown high yielding ability and stability for 3 yr (Table 2). ■

Table 2. Yield of IET8717 and Manoharsali under continuous waterlogging. Titabar, Assam, India, 1987-89.

Year	IET8717		Manoharsali	
	Yield (t/ha)	Duration (d)	Yield (t/ha)	Duration (d)
1987	5.0	144	2.5	162
1988	4.8	144	2.7	163
1989	5.0	143	3.5	163